

Solubility of Calcium Sulphate in the Binary NaCl-H₂O and Ternary NaCl-MgSO₄-H₂O Systems

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The solubility of calcium sulphate in different concentrations of sodium chloride and magnesium sulphate have been determined at 25, 35 and 100°. The calcium sulphate occurs as its dehydrate at lower temperatures but at higher temperatures as its anhydrate in the solid phase. The study has been extended to the solubility of calcium sulphate in the system NaCl-H₂O and NaCl-MgSO₄-H₂O. Further, it has been applied to interpret the solubility of calcium sulphate with increasing density of sea water brine and underground brines in view of the multi-ions occurring in them.

Solubility of calcium sulphate which is mainly dependent on temperature and concentration of the dissolved species, plays an important role in the intensity of scale-formation of calcium sulphate in desalination plants, electro dialysis units and in boilers etc. It also occurs in salt, but in the production of high purity salt for chemical industries particularly soda ash, caustic soda and chlorine industries, it is considered as an impurity. These industries demand for high purity salt, virtually with no calcium and magnesium content or at least with very low concentrations of calcium (in ppm) and magnesium as they are washable. As mentioned earlier, the magnesium content can be washed out whereas the calcium content cannot be easily removed. Thus, an insight into the solubility of calcium sulphate in the temperature range of 0-200° is of utmost importance. Many authors¹⁻⁴ studied some of the aqueous salt systems having calcium sulphate as one of the components. Susarla⁵ *et al.*⁵ investigated the ternary systems of CaSO₄-NaCl-H₂O at ambient temperatures. These studies have been further extended to study the systems (CaSO₄-NaCl-MgSO₄-H₂O) at 25, 35 and 100° with a view of applying these data in predicting the solubility of calcium sulphate in sea water and underground brines particularly at the density at which the separation of salt (NaCl) starts during the solar evaporation of these brines. This in turn helps in producing solar salt with very low calcium content which can be of great use to chemical industries. It also gives an overall idea in the development of suitable thermodynamic model to get an insight into the various ionic (multi-ionic) forces occurring and thus throw some light on the competitive forces between calcium, magnesium, sodium cations and sulphate and chloride anions. The above studies can also help in knowing (i) the effect of increasing concentration of magnesium ion on the solubility of calcium sulphate and (ii) the effect of increasing concentration of ions of magnesium, sodium on the solubility of calcium sulphate as their sulphates and chlorides.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results of molal solubilities of calcium sulphate against the square-root of the ionic strength in the system CaSO₄-NaCl-MgSO₄-H₂O are given in Table 1 and Fig. 1 at 25, 35 and 100°. With increase in concentra-

Fig. 1. Solubility of calcium sulphate versus ionic strength in CaSO₄-NaCl-MgSO₄-H₂O system at 25, 35 and 100°.

tion of sodium chloride and magnesium sulphate, the solubility of calcium sulphate shows a decreasing trend initially upto the ionic strength of 1.7921 and then further onwards shows an increase with increasing concentration of magnesium sulphate. The initial decrease in solubility is attributed to the common-ion effect (here sulphate) but after certain concentration of magnesium sulphate when the ionic strength exceeds 1.7921, it shows an increase which may be due to diverse-ion effect. This effect is in agreement with the reported data^{1,3}.

In practice the thermodynamic solubility of calcium sulphate dihydrate can be presented as

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITIES OF CALCIUM SULPHATE AGAINST IONIC STRENGTHS IN CaSO₄-NaCl-MgSO₄-H₂O SYSTEM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

25°		35°		100°	
Molality of CaSO ₄ in solution phase	\sqrt{I} molal units	Molality of CaSO ₄ in solution phase	\sqrt{I} molal units	Molality of CaSO ₄ in solution phase	\sqrt{I} molal units
0.0413 ^a	1.7479	0.0429	1.7463	0.0452	1.7442
0.0109 ^b	1.6763				
0.0224	1.7871	0.0154	1.6779	0.0131 ^b	1.7271
0.0321	2.7690	0.0147	1.7652	0.0281	1.8096
0.0343	1.9255	0.0115 ^b	1.6823	0.0321	1.9256
0.0356	2.0667	0.0112	1.7921	0.0349	1.6206
0.0387	2.7801	0.0140	1.8721	0.0389	2.3377
0.0421	2.4649	0.0170	2.2430	0.0389	2.3529
0.0427	2.4313	0.0213	2.1823	0.0401	2.5050
0.0417	3.0277	0.0210	2.4695	0.0394	2.5423

^aSolution saturated with both NaCl and CaSO₄ salts. ^bSolution saturated with three salts NaCl, CaSO₄ and MgSO₄.

At lower temperatures calcium sulphate occurs as CaSO₄.2H₂O and at higher temperatures as CaSO₄ (anhydrite) only in the solid phase. Ionic strength, $I = \sum 1/2 C_i Z_i^2$, where C_i (concentration of the salt) is expressed in molalities and Z the valence of the ion.

and the thermodynamic equilibrium constant can be written as

$$K_{SP(T)} = a_{Ca^{2+}} a_{SO_4^{2-}} a_{H_2O}^2$$

$$K_{SP(T)} = m_{Ca^{2+}} m_{SO_4^{2-}} \gamma_{Ca^{2+}} \gamma_{SO_4^{2-}} a_{H_2O}^2 \quad (2)$$

But

$$K_{SP(P)} = m_{Ca^{2+}} m_{SO_4^{2-}} \quad (3)$$

where, $K_{SP(P)}$ is the ion solubility product, $\gamma_{Ca^{2+}}$ and $\gamma_{SO_4^{2-}}$ are the ion activity coefficients, $m_{Ca^{2+}}$ and $m_{SO_4^{2-}}$ the molal concentrations of calcium and sulphate ions and a is the activity of water. Equation (2) reduces to

$$K_{SP(T)} = K_{SP(P)} \gamma_{Ca^{2+}} \gamma_{SO_4^{2-}} a_{H_2O}^2 \quad (4)$$

If the activity of water is taken into account and equals to unity, then the true solubility product at any temperature can be written as

$$K_{SP(T)} = K_{SP(P)} \gamma_{Ca^{2+}} \gamma_{SO_4^{2-}} \quad (5)$$

and $K_{SP(T)} = K_{SP(P)}$

Thus we can say that $K_{SP(T)} \rightarrow K_{SP(P)}$, when the activity of water approaches unity and when the activities of ions also approach unity. With the help of Debye-Hückel equation and with the inclusion of some more mathematical terms to consider other factors like electrostatic forces existing between the charged particles like cations, anions etc., viscosity of the solvent (here water) and the formation of multi-ion forces occurring in the system, the insolubility product as given by Marshall and Slusher³ can

be written as

$$\log K_{SP(T)} = \log K_{SP(P)} + \frac{8S\sqrt{I}}{1 + A\sqrt{I}} + BI + CI^2 \quad (6)$$

which can be applied to electrolytic solution having higher ionic strengths, wherein S is the product of the Debye-Hückel constant and the slope of the square-root of density of solvent (here water) and I the ionic strength of the solution ($I = 1/2 \sum C_i Z_i^2$) and the constant A , B and C are adjustable parameters. The values for these constants have been taken from the literature wherein the formation of multi-ion-pairs like $Ca(SO_4)_3^{2-}$, $NaSO_4^-$, $Ca_2(SO_4)_2^{2+}$ etc. have been taken into account in the terms BI and CI^2 . Equation (6) gives a satisfactory explanation for the deviation of calcium sulphate solubility at higher ionic strengths and thus gives an idea of the solubility of calcium sulphate in the presence of large amounts of sodium chloride and magnesium sulphate. This value of the solubility product of calcium sulphate should be considered for all practical purposes particularly in discussing about it in the multi-ion equilibria.

These data have been applied to the stagewise solubility of calcium sulphate in sea water and underground brines of Sonerai creek of Bhavnagar. As the evaporation of sea water, brine and bittern takes place in the range 30–45° in the solar evaporation for producing salt and the bittern, the 35° data have been used for comparison. The analytical results of the samples are given in Table 2 and the plots of square-root of solubility of calcium sulphate versus square-root of the ionic strength are shown in Fig. 2 with the solubility data at 35°. As the sea water is subjected for solar

Fig. 2. Square root of solubility of calcium sulphate vs ionic strength in CaSO₄-NaCl-MgSO₄ system at 35°.

evaporation to get salt, the concentration of calcium sulphate initially increases and then shows a decrease, whereas in case of underground brines of Bhavnagar it goes on decreasing right from the beginning as can be seen from the graph. This happens because in case of underground brines, the initial concentration of calcium sulphate is higher

TABLE 2—STAGEWISE SOLUBILITY OF CALCIUM SULPHATE IN SEA WATER AND UNDERGROUND BRINES (SONERAI CREEK, BHAVNAGAR) WITH INCREASE IN IONIC STRENGTH

Source of brine	Sea water					Bhavnagar brine (Sonerai creek)			
	3.5	10.0	17.0	24.0	29.0	14.0	20.0	25.0	29.0
Degree baume	3.5	10.0	17.0	24.0	29.0	14.0	20.0	25.0	29.0
Density	1.025	1.074	1.134	1.200	1.251	1.107	1.161	1.214	1.251
\sqrt{C} in molal unit	0.3826	0.6329	0.6763	0.3943	0.1844	0.7210	0.6630	0.5290	0.2236
\sqrt{I} in molal unit	0.2604	0.6589	0.6455	0.7742	1.0070	0.5653	0.6629	0.6348	0.8522

than in sea water and of course it also depends on site and location of the borewell. It can be seen (Fig. 2) that the addition of sea bittern to the underground brines can be of definite help in reducing the calcium sulphate content coming in salt, thereby increasing the purity of salt for various industrial uses. The excess magnesium salts that comes can be washed out by rains and/or by employing other purifying techniques.

The data when interpreted in the light of equation (6) gives a satisfactory explanation to the solubility of calcium sulphate at high concentrations of sodium chloride as can be seen in Fig. 1. The molal solubility values of calcium sulphate in the system $\text{CaSO}_4\text{-NaCl-MgSO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ agree well at lower ionic strengths. As predicted earlier by others¹⁻⁴ and observed by us, the deviation in solubility of calcium sulphate at high ionic strengths can be explained with the formation of ion-pairs like divalent, trivalent and multi-ion types that occur in the system.

Experimental

Double-distilled deionised water and A.R. grade chemicals were used. Known amounts of sodium chloride were added to the stock solutions of magnesium sulphate (500 g) and the concentrations expressed in molalities. The resulting solutions mixed with an excess calcium sulphate solutions were stirred in a thermostatically controlled wa-

ter-bath. After the solutions were stirred with an electrical paddle for about 24 h at the specified temperature (25, 35 and 100°). Liquid samples were drawn periodically and analysed for calcium and magnesium (by EDTA), chloride (Vochard) and sulphate (gravimetry). Sodium was determined by flame photometry (Evans Electro Selenium Ltd.) at λ_{max} 589.2 nm. Similar methods were employed in analysing the composition of the solid phase by drawing solid phase samples.

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